

Leaf Area Index (LAI) at the Hartheim Forest Research Site (DE-Har) 2021 – 2025

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1 Abstract

Leaf area index (LAI) was estimated at the Hartheim Forest Research Site (ICOS Ecosystem Site “DE-Har”) yearly in the growing season between 2021 and 2025. Measurements were performed using the LAI-2000 Plant Canopy Analyzer by LICOR, with data collected from multiple measurement points inside and outside the fenced area of the station during twilight or under overcast cloud cover. The methodology involves simultaneous above- and below-canopy radiation measurements, followed by data processing and statistical analysis. Results show that average estimated LAI values over the four years 2021-2025 are relatively consistent with an average of 2.6 m²/m² (2.2-2.9 m²/m²) and a median of 2.4 m²/m². As the upper canopy consists of a substantial number of standing dead pines, LAI could be overestimated using this method.

2 Purpose of report

The purpose of this technical report is to document the measurement protocol and technical procedures used to estimate LAI at the Hartheim Forest Research Site and to report the estimated LAI values for annual measurements taken in the growing seasons between 2021 and 2025.

3 Methods

3.1 Measurement site characteristics

The Hartheim Forest Research Site is an associated ecosystem research station in the Integrated Carbon Observation System (ICOS) and part of ICOS Germany (code “DE-Har”). The site is located in the Upper Rhine Valley in an alluvial plain near the river Rhine in Hartheim am Rhein, Baden-Württemberg, Germany (Longitude: 7.59814°, Latitude: 47.93391°, Elevation: 201 m a.s.l.) The forest has an upper canopy of planted Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris*) and European black pines (*Pinus nigra*), many of them dead due to recurring droughts (Haberstroh et al., 2022; Plapp et al., 2024). The mid-canopy has various deciduous tree species, including *Tilia sp.*, *Carpinus betulus*, *Fagus sylvatica*, *Acer platanoides*, *Crataegus laevigata*, and *Prunus sp.* (Plapp et al., 2024).

The Hartheim Research Site has two towers, a measurement hut and has been providing continuous meteorological measurements since 1978. The towers stand within a fenced area of 0.7 ha (Mayer et al., 2014). Due to the fence, there is no damage from excessive browsing by deer and other game, which is more common in the tower source area outside the fence.

3.2 Plant canopy measurement principle

Measurements were taken using LI-COR LAI-2000 Plant Canopy Analyzers. The LI-COR LAI-2000 measures light in different elevation angles to measure plant area density (PAI). Two LAI-2000 devices were employed simultaneously in the “Remote mode”. We attached one device (A) and its light sensor at the top of a 30 m tower to measure incoming radiation above the canopy. We attached another device (B) and its light sensor to a rake handle at a height of 2.2 m, so we could rest the end on the ground while standing and make the measuring process easier (Figure 1). Before taking each measurement, the light sensor was aligned horizontally using the bubble level integrated in the sensor (Figure 2). Details and instructions on the programming are given in Appendix A.

After the measurements, the FV-2200 software (Appendix A) compared light levels measured above the canopy to the light measured below the canopy and uses the difference between the two to model the PAI which is considered equal to the LAI.

Figure 1: Measurements taken with device B at 2.2 m below canopy on the path to the measurement hut in 2024

Figure 2: LAI-2000 device with release button and sensor

3.3 Measurement dates

Measurements are taken at the peak of the growing season in July, except in 2023 when measurements were in late September but before senescence and in 2025 when measurements were taken in late June (Table 1). Measurements were taken under overcast conditions (2024) or with the sun near horizon / evening twilight (2021-2023, 2025).

Table 1: Measurement dates, times and number of locations and samples taken for LAI-2000 measurements at the Hartheim Forest Research Site (DE-Har) between 2021 and 2025.

Year	Measurement Date	Measurement time from	Measurement time to	Number of locations	Number of valid samples
2021	2021-07-10	19:58	20:44	33	160
2022	2022-07-28	20:05	20:15	26	125
2023	2023-09-26	17:46	18:02	36	179
2024	2024-07-01	10:15	10:51	36	180
2025	2025-06-25	20:45	21:03	36	180

3.4 Measurement layout

At each measuring point below canopy, five measurements were taken with device B. There were 36 measurement points resulting in 180 total measurements but due to technical problems and data quality not always all 180 measuring points were recorded. The measurements were organized into six rows with six measurement points each. Each measurement point within a given row was approximately 10 m apart, and each row was approximately 5 m apart. The first row was on the gravel path towards the hut on the field site, and the following five rows went eastward from this path.

Figure 3: Six rows in which six measurements each were taken at a distance of approximately 10 m each

4 Results

Averaged estimated LAI values for each measurement date are summarized in Table 2. The averaged LAI for all years 2021-2025 was estimated $2.62 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^2$ and the average median of all years was estimated $2.35 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^2$. Using the conditional average for values only between the 10th and 90th percentile, the average LAI was $2.56 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^2$. LAI was lowest for the 2023 measurement which was taken later in the year (in September), hence could have been influenced by the yearly course of LAI. The year 2025 resulted in highest LAI estimation (+10%). Measurements include the broadleaf understory, but the upper canopy consists of a substantial number of standing dead pines (Plapp et al. 2024), consequently the assumption that LAI is equal to PAI could lead to an overestimation of the LAI in this stand.

Table 2: LAI measurement characteristics for each of the measurements and multi-year averages of LAI

Year	Measurement Date	Average LAI (m^2/m^2)	Conditionally Averaged LAI (m^2/m^2)	Median LAI (m^2/m^2)	LAI 10 th Percentile (m^2/m^2)	LAI 90 th Percentile (m^2/m^2)
2021	2021-07-28	2.81	2.76	2.37	1.41	4.56
2022	2022-07-10	2.66	2.60	2.32	1.54	4.53
2023	2023-09-26	2.16	2.11	2.10	1.38	3.05
2024	2024-07-01	2.60	2.56	2.36	1.21	4.34
2025	2025-06-25	2.88	2.79	2.60	1.43	4.84
Average	2021-2025	2.62	2.56	2.35		

Figure 4: Distribution and cumulative probability for each of the measurement campaigns from 2021 to 2025

Values submitted to ICOS ETC are the median values in Table 2.

Appendix

Appendix A: Documentation of device settings

Setting up devices before measurements

For the PAI measurement implementation, two LI-COR LAI-2000 Plant Canopy Analyzers (devices) are required and operated simultaneously. Device “A” is used above canopy on the tower and device “B” is used mobile below canopy. These devices are each attached at the X-port to an LAI-2050 sensor, which measures light at different elevation angles. The program compares the light measured in different elevation angles above the canopy (A) to simultaneously measured values below the canopy (B) and uses the difference between the two to estimate the amount of plant canopy cover (Licor, 1992). To set up the devices to take measurements, the following steps are required:

1. Turn on devices A and B.
2. Use *FCT 24* on devices A and B to erase all previous data.

3. Use *FCT 21* on devices A and B to check if all previous data has been erased (Free Memory = 100%).
4. Use *FCT 05* on devices A and B to ensure both devices show the same correct time and date. Press *ENTER*.
5. Use *FCT 11* on device A to check:
 - a. Mode: “Remote Above X,”
 - b. Log Int: 15 sec,
 - c. Input the start time (can be some minutes before data collection with device B starts. Keep the gaps in the Display (hh_mm_ss), move the cursor with the arrows),
 - d. Input the end time (can be some minutes after data collection with device B ends),
 - e. Number of files: 1 (may change depending on total time input).
6. Optional: Use *FCT 12* on device A to set prompts (page 3-10 of the instruction manual):
 - a. Prompt 1 =
 - i. NEW = WHAT
 - ii. Press *ENTER*
 - b. Prompt 2 =
 - i. NEW = WHERE
 - ii. Press *ENTER*
7. Use *FCT 14* on device A to respond to the prompts and name the file:
 - a. Confirm the file name by entering it twice.
8. Use *FCT 11* on device B to check:
 - a. Mode: “Remote Below X,”
 - b. # Ave=0,
 - c. NEW = leave empty

Combining files after measurements

After taking measurements with devices A and B, they must be combined and then transferred to a computer to calculate the plant area index (PAI) which is considered equal to the LAI.

This requires the following steps:

1. Use *FCT 35* to enter device A into slave mode. Enter the number of the file containing A readings. (with our setup enter “1”)
2. Use *FCT 34* to complete the remote files in device B. On device B, enter the range of files that will require A readings from the file on device A.
 - a. REPLACE = ?
 - b. REPLACE WITH = A
 - c. STORE AS OLD = NO. This transforms the merged file into a new file while preserving the original.
 - d. Connect device A and device B together using a null modem cable (see Photo).
 - e. When “Press any key when connected” is displayed, press *ENTER* to begin the process.

Figure 5: Null modem cable used to connect device A and B

Wait while records in the B files are replaced with A records from device A.

3. Once the process is finished (takes approximately 10min), press *BREAK* on device A to exit slave mode. Disconnect the devices.
4. Optional: Use *FCT 16* on device B to remove bad readings, which are defined as any B value higher than its corresponding A value. The options are:
 - a. Beep, Ignore: skips any bad readings. The device beeps when this occurs.
 - i. This is the setting that we use at Hartheim.
 - b. Set A/B = 1: sets any transmittance greater than 1.0 to be equal to 1.0. A records are used as the above-canopy records.

- c. Set B/A = 1: sets any transmittance greater than 1.0 to be equal to 1.0. B records are used as the above-canopy records.
5. Use *FCT 26* on device B to compute the completed files. Enter the completed file number.
6. Use *FCT 33* on device B to set the format to the standard option.
 - a. FORMAT: Standard
 - b. PRNT OBS: YES

Transferring data to a computer

7. Install / open the FV-2200 software on a Windows computer (Software download: <https://www.licor.com/env/support/LAI-2200C/software>)
8. Connect device B to the computer with the RS232 cable and the USB converter (Figure 5):

Figure 6: Connection cable between LAI-2000 and PC

Run the FV-2200 software on the PC and then

- a. Click “Acquire.”
- b. Select the type of LAI device used.
 - i. We used an LAI-2000 device.

Figure 7: Connection process in the FV-2200 software

9. Use *FCT 32* to print and transfer the data from device B to the computer.
10. Wait for the data to transfer.
11. Once the data finishes transferring, check the data.
 - a. Make sure the PAI value is greater than 0.
 - b. Make sure the data values are labelled with alternating “A” and “B” labels. If the “A” values are instead labelled with “?”, the data may not have been correctly combined between the devices.
12. Double-click on the file that appears in the box. Click *Copy to clipboard* and paste it into a blank Microsoft Excel file.

Figure 8: Data output and copying in the FV-2200 software

Appendix B: Calculations

We used formulas in Microsoft Excel to analyze data and calculate statistics:

1. Minimum, maximum, mean, median, conditional mean, 10th and 90th inclusive percentile, and the 25th and 75th exclusive percentile LAI and gap (1–5) values:
 - a. Minimum:
=MIN (range of all 180 LAI or gap values)
 - b. Maximum:
=MAX (range of all 180 LAI or gap values)
 - c. Mean:
=AVERAGE (range of all 180 LAI or gap values)
 - d. Median:
=MEDIAN (range of all 180 LAI or gap values)
 - e. Conditional mean:
=AVERAGEIFS (range of all 180 LAI or gap values, range of all 180 LAI or gap values, ">" & 10th percentile LAI or gap value, range of all 180 LAI or gap values, "<" & 90th percentile LAI or gap value)
 - f. 10th inclusive percentile:
=PERCENTILE.INC (range of all 180 LAI or gap values, 0.1)
 - g. 25th exclusive percentile:
=PERCENTILE.EXC (range of all 180 LAI or gap values, 0.25)
 - h. 75th exclusive percentile:
=PERCENTILE.EXC (range of all 180 LAI or gap values, 0.75)
 - i. 90th inclusive percentile:
=PERCENTILE.INC (range of all 180 LAI or gap values, 0.9)
2. The relative and cumulative frequencies (as a percentage) of LAI values at 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, 3.0, 3.5, 4.0, 4.5, and 5.0:
 - a. Relative and cumulative frequencies of LAI 0.5:
=(=FREQUENCY (range of all 180 LAI or gap values, T13:T22)) /180*100

- i. Where **T13 : T22** = cells containing the values 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, 3.0, 3.5, 4.0, 4.5, and 5.0.
- b. Relative frequencies of LAI 1.0–5.0:
$$= (\text{FREQUENCY}(\text{range of all 180 LAI or gap values, T13 : T22})) / 180 * 100$$
- c. Cumulative frequency of LAI 1.0:
$$= (\text{relative frequency of LAI 1.0}) + (\text{cumulative frequency of LAI 0.5})$$
- d. Cumulative frequency of LAI 1.5–5.0: same formula as above (2c), replacing the LAI 1.0 relative frequency value with the relative frequency value of the given LAI value, and the 0.5 LAI cumulative frequency value with the cumulative frequency value of the previous LAI value.

Appendix C: Link to data repositories

Data tables including the individual point measurements are available as digital open data on www.zenodo.org under:

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15066488>

References

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